

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Review On Dengue Virus Prevention And Treatment

Lamkhade Kanchan S.*, Lamkhade Sandhya V., Fatakkar Renuka B. , Gahire Pratiksha D. , Umbarde Rupali P.

Dr. Ithape Institute Of B. Pharmacy ,Sangamner ,Dist. Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, 422605 ,India

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05 March 2024

Accepted: 09 March 2024

Published: 13 March 2024

Keywords:

Dengue, Prevention,
Treatment.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10814984

ABSTRACT

Dengue is an acute viral illness caused by RNA contagion of the family Flaviviridae and spread by Aedes mosquitoes. Presenting features may range from asymptomatic fever to dreaded complications similar as hemorrhagic fever and shock. A cute- onset high fever, muscle and joint pain, myalgia, cutaneous rash, hemorrhagic occurrences, and circulatory shock are the generally seen symptoms. Oral instantiations are rare in dengue infection; still, some cases may have oral features as the only presenting incarnation. Beforehand and accurate opinion is critical to reduce mortality. Dengue is wide throughout the tropics and original spatial variation in dengue contagion transmission is explosively told by downfall, temperature, urbanization and distribution of the top mosquito vector Aedes aegypti. presently, aboriginal dengue contagion transmission is reported in the Eastern Mediterranean, American, South- East Asian, Western Pacific and African regions, whereas sporadic original transmission has been reported in Europe and the United States as the result of contagion preface to areas where Ae. aegypti and Aedes albopictus, a secondary vector, do. The global burden of the complaint isn't well known, but its epidemiological patterns are intimidating for both mortal health and the global frugality.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization(WHO) consider dengue as a major global public health challenge in the tropic and tropical nations. Dengue has seen a30-fold upsurge worldwide between 1960 and 2010, due to increased population growth rate, global warming, unplanned urbanization, hamstrung mosquito control, frequent air trip, and lack of health care installations () Dengue is

presently one of the world's most important neglected tropical conditions. and its prevalence has increased>30-fold in recent decades alongside the geographical expansion of the Aedes vector mosquitoes and dengue contagions(DENVs) Dengue hemorrhagic fever(DHF/ DSS) is the most severe incarnation of the complaint in children who have a secondary infection with a different serotype than the first one. DF is a tone-

***Corresponding Author:** Lamkhade Kanchan S.

Address: *Dr.Ithape Institute Of B.Pharmacy ,Sangamner ,Dist.Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, 422605 ,India*

Email ✉: kanchanlamkhade26@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

limiting complaint, meaning the case will recover with no sequelae once the fever is gone. Dengue haemorrhagic fever (DHF) is a serious febrile illness characterized by haemostasis abnormalities and elevated vascular permeability. Severe progression may lead to DSS (dengue shock pattern). There are four grades of DHF, the third and fourth being DSS. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there are further than 50 million infections of dengue contagion and 20,000 deaths related to dengue complaint. What's the dengue conditions Dengue is a contagion-grounded infection majorly predominant in the tropical regions of the world. The womanish Aedes mosquito is the vector that transmits dengue causing contagion cells from infected people to healthy people through blood-stinking mouthfuls. The contagion also transfers from the vector and enters the host to fleetly reproduce dengue causing contagions opinion and treatment of Dengue Dengue contagion can beget symptoms ranging from mild to severe. roughly 1 in 4 infections with Dengue contagion is characteristic. The most common symptom of a characteristic Dengue contagion infection is a mild or moderate, acute, feverish illness.

Fig 1. pathogenesis dengue contagion and infection
Types of dengue :

About 40 of the population of the 100 countries where Dengue is aboriginal are susceptible

toDengue.However, the chances of early recovery are high, If the opinion is made in the early stages. Depending on the inflexibility and the symptoms observed in the host,

Dengue is classified into :

- Mild Dengue Fever
- Dengue Haemorrhagic fever
- Dengue Shock Pattern

Nature Reviews | Disease Primers

Fig 2. The civic dengue contagion cycle in humans and mosquitoes.

During the foreign phase of the cycle, dengue contagions first infect mosquito midgut cells and other apkins before propagating to the salivary dears Bracket The World Health Organization (WHO) divides DF into two orders uncomplicated and severe. Severe DF cases are associated with inordinate bleeding, organ damage, or severe tube leakage, while the remainder are uncomplicated Symptoms

- High Fever(40 °C/ 104 °F)
- Severe Headache
- Pain Behind The Eyes
- Muscle And Joint Pains * Nausea
- Puking
- Blown Glands
- Rash.
- Severe Stomach Pain
- Patient Puking

- Bleeding From Your Epoxies Or Nose * Blood In Your Urine, Droppings Or Heave
- Bleeding Under The Skin, Which Might Look Like Bruising * Delicate Or Rapid-Fire Breathing * Fatigue
- Perversity Or Restlessness(15) CLINICAL Instantiations Undifferentiated Fever Acute Undifferentiated Fever(AUF) Is Defined As Measured Temperature ≥ 38 °C May Be Associated With Symptoms Similar As Abdominal Pain Diarrhoea Hematocrit Nausea Or Puking Rhinorrhea Breathlessness Ocular Pain Altered Sensorium Headache Cervical Stiffness Rash Muscle Pang Petechiae Eccchymosis Nose Or Goo Bleeding Jaundice Auf Is Distinct From Pyrexia, Which Is A Fever Of At Least Three Weeks With No Specific Cause, Indeed After Disquisition. Dengue Fever Dengue Fever(DF) Is Caused By A Combination Of Primary And Secondary Infections. It's Most Generally Set Up In Grown-Ups And In Aged Children.

Dengue fever is a wide complaint in tropical and sub-tropical climates. It's a major problem in numerous countries in Latin America, as well as in Southeast Asia. Although Dengue fever is uncommon in the United States, it's present in some American homes, similar as Puerto Rico(Puerto Rico), American Samoa(American Samoa), and the United States Virgin Islands(American Samoa). Dengue fever can also do in the United States when someone becomes infected in another country, and also moves or emigrates to the United States. Dengue hemorrhagic fever This is called severe dengue, dengue hemorrhagic fever or dengue shock pattern. Severe dengue be when your blood vessels come damaged and leaky. The proposed individual criteria for DHF includes. Clinical Parameters Acute-onset fever High-grade fever lasting between 2 days and 1 week Hemorrhagic occurrences Petechiae,

Purpura, Ecchymosis, Epistaxis, Gingival and Mucosal Bleeding, GIT or Injection point, Hematemesis, Malena B. Laboratory parameters Thrombocytopenia(platelet count $< 100,000$ / cu mm) Prevention and Risk Factors

- Dengue Prevention(Centers For Disease Control And Prevention) * Also In Spanish
- Find The Repellent That's Right For You(Environmental Protection Agency)
- For Parents A Safe-Deposit Box And Effective Vaccine To Help Dengue Is Available(Centers For Disease Control And Prevention)
- Help Control Mosquitoes That Spread Dengue, Chikungunya, And Zika Viruses(Centers For Disease Control And Prevention)
- Also In Spanish
- Cover Against Mosquito Mouthfuls When Traveling(Centers For Disease Control And Prevention)
- Clothes That Cover As Important Of Your Body As Possible
- Mosquito Nets If Sleeping During The Day, Immaculately Nets Scattered With Nonentity Repellent
- Window Defenses
- Mosquito Repellents(Containing DEET, Picaridin Or IR3535)
- Coils And Vaporizers. Still, It's Important To If You Get Dengue.
- Rest Drink Plenitude Of Liquids
- Use Acetaminophen(Paracetamol) For Pain
- Avoid non-Steroidal anti-Inflammatory Medicines, Like Ibuprofen And Aspirin
- Watch For Severe Symptoms And Communicate Your Croaker As Soon As Possible If You Notice Any.

Factors involved in the control of dengue contagion complaint response.

Nature Reviews | Disease Primers

3. Factor control dengue

Four main factors control dengue contagion (DENV) complaint response along a response continuum vulnerable status, contagion strain, inheritable status and age. Immune status Recovery from infection by one dengue contagion provides lifelong impunity against that particular contagion serotype. still, this impunity confers only partial and flash protection against posterior infection by the other three serotypes of the virus. Polyclonal antibodies are directed against several epitopes; some are directed against

quaternary epitopes located at the hinge region between DI and DII of the E protein on the face of complete virions. The maturity of circulating antibodies arenon-neutralizing and are directed against colorful antigens on the E protein and the prM protein. In the absence of blocking by type-specific negating antibodies, non-neutralizing antibodies generally enhance the entry of any DENV into Fc receptor-bearing cells. This miracle is called antibody-dependent improvement (ADE)

Viral serotypes-

To date, utmost of the inheritable changes associated with epidemic eventuality have redounded in amino acid changes in NS proteins. Several pathogenesis studies have been performed

on cases with dengue who were clinically classified as having either dengue fever or DHF/DSS3. Although both dengue fever and DHF/DSS can be associated with any serotype, some sequences of infection have been associated with

severe complaint at a advanced frequency than others.

REFERENCES

1. Gubler DJ. Dengue and dengue Hemorrhagic fever. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 1998; 11:480 – 96.(PMC free composition)
2. New ed. Geneva, Switzerland World Health Organization; 2009. World Health Organization(WHO). Dengue- Guidelines for opinion, Treatment, Prevention and Control.
3. Guzman MG, Halstead SB, Artsob H, Buchy P, Farrar J, Gubler DJ, et al. Dengue A continuing global trouble. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2010; 8(Suppl) S7 – 16.(PMC free composition)
4. Guzman,M.G. & Harris,E. Dengue. *Lancet* 385, 453 – 465(2015). A veritably comprehensive review of the rearmost findings on the global burden of dengue between 2010 and 2015. Composition PubMed Google Scholar
5. World Health Organization & Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical conditions. Dengue Guidelines for opinion, Treatment, Prevention and Control. WHO http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/44188/1/9789241547871_eng.pdf(2009). This document includes recommendations for the bracket and operation of cases with dengue.
6. World Health Organization. Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever opinion, Treatment, Prevention and Control 2nd edn(WHO Press, 1997).
7. Shepard DS, Suaya JA, Halstead SB, Nathan MB, Gubler DJ, Mahoney RT, Wang DNC, Meltzer MI. Cost- effectiveness of a pediatric dengue Vaccine. 2004; 22:1275 – 1280.
8. Mackenzie JS, Gubler DJ, Petersen LR. Arising flaviviruses the spread and rejuvenescence of Japanese encephalitis, West Nile and dengue contagions. *Nat Med.* 2004; 10:S98 – S109.
9. Geneva, Switzerland World Health Organization; 2009. WHO. Dengue Guidelines for opinion, Treatment, Prevention and Control. Part1.1.6 Dengue case bracket;pp. 10 – 2
10. [https// FU](https://FU), Mahmood CB, Sharma JD, Hoque SM, Zaman R, Hasan MH. Dengue fever and dengue haemorrhagic fever in children the 2000 out break in Chittatong, Bangladesh. *Dengue Bulletin.* 2001; 25:33 – 9
11. Fibriansah,G. et al. Dengue contagion. Cryo-EM structure of an antibody that neutralizes dengue contagion type 2 by locking E protein dimers. *Science* 349, 88 – 91(2015).
12. de Alwis,R. et al. In- depth analysis of the antibody response of individualities exposed to primary dengue contagion infection. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 5, e1188(2011).
13. de Alwis,R. et al. Dengue contagions are enhanced by distinct populations of serotypecross-reactive antibodies in mortal vulnerable sera. *PLoS Pathog.* 10, e1004386(2014).
14. Guzman,M.G., Alvarez,M. & Halstead,S.B. Secondary infection as a threat factor for dengue hemorrhagic fever/ dengue shock pattern an literal perspective and part of antibody-dependent improvement of infection. *Arch. Virol.* 158, 1445 – 1459(2013).

HOW TO CITE: Lamkhade Kanchan S., Lamkhade Sandhya V., Fatakkar Renuka B. , Gahire Pratiksha D. , Umbarde Rupali P., Review On Dengue Virus Prevention And Treatment, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 3, 413-417. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814984>

